

Fasting, Failure and Addiction in Metrified Academia

notes from the front line of art-science crossover education

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Artwork from the musical group Ministry

At a meeting, around 13 years ago, I got into a conversation with colleagues about how the scientific landscape had changed with the rise of publication metrics (e.g., publications per year and citation counts for individuals; impact factors for journals). We agreed that we needed to fight against the detrimental effects of metrification. I recently found a note on my lap top that I had meant to send to those colleagues but never did. It reminded me that my fight was a short-lived failure. It also triggered a realization as to a cause of the failure.

Note from 2010ish: Here's a beer bet I am wondering if anyone wants to agree to. It's a personal bet between me and me at this stage - an experiment. I have found myself getting obsessed with what I was never a fan of: Bean Counting. In a personal Zen-like fast I am seeing how long I can go without checking any citation statistics or the like. I will update my vitae, remain active and produce science but I will resist tracking metrics. I started Jan 1 and am still living clean (it's now September). I found it hard going at first and told myself the desire to check my metrics was just to see who was doing similar work, to see how useful the work was, and other justifications that fell short of reality. The exercise has isolated lies I was telling myself about why I wanted to check the numbers.

Jump to Today: I had all but forgotten the note above until 2020 provided an unexpected break from my usual "to-do job list". Finding the note was a bit of personal archeology. My memory came back to something I had blocked out. My bean counting fast ended in failure. While into the fast, my department chair stated that all of us should open a ResearchGate account. ResearchGate is a commercial social networking site for scientists and researchers. It lets papers be shared but it also tracks metrics. I opened an account and quickly fell from grace. I reverted back to tracking my productivity metrics with, what I can only describe as, a drug-like delight. The delight was mixed with associated hangovers and emotional let downs. I fell back to comparing my metrics against others, as if that would provide some satisfaction. Often it led to the opposite.

Why would I be so easily drawn back to something I do not value? How could I become so easily re-obsessed with something that might cause cheap delight but comes with a price of feeling bad about myself? I could say I need to do some professional things that I do not agree with ethically to survive in my field. That's not really the real reason.

The reason I came to is that I had become an addict. I offer no solution other than that seeing an addiction may be a start toward controlling it. From what I know of addiction therapy, a key aspect is to realize 'once an addict, always an addict'. That is, there is always the potential of falling back into an addiction if you do not remain aware of it.

My 2020 looking up from my usual job tasks also got me researching what others have said about changing landscapes that come with the metrification of science and, more broadly, academia. Much of the metrification is driven by universities moving toward corporate models of operation and an associated privatization of what were once public goods. That research has continued, at varied cadence, to the present day. It led me to run across a quote in 2023 that crystalized some thoughts and led to this essay. The quote comes from someone, outside of my own field, who also experienced a self-realization about tracking their citations (from *Learn to Write Badly: How to Succeed in the Social Sciences* by Michael Billing, 2013):

Why, I might ask, am I bothering to find out how many times other academics have mentioned my work? And why do I feel pleased if the number is high? What difference does it make? It doesn't seem to matter how the others are mentioning me, whether they do so in passing or at length, whether its complimentary or critical tones. All that matters is that I am mentioned, again and again. It gets worse. Sometimes, I have compared my scores with those of others. I am pleased if I am mentioned in more articles than they are, and my mood will be spoiled if their numbers surpass mine. It is as if I am pathetically pleading with the academic world: 'Please, please mention me; you only need mention me in passing; just drop my name; I don't care where or how; just mention me, please; oh, and don't bother mentioning Dr X or Professor Y.' Do I really think like this? Do I really care about the numbers? Yes, I must do. What a knob head.

What a knob head, indeed – I am speaking of myself. I have not met Michael Billing so I do not know this for sure but I wonder, based on my own experience, if he saw calling himself a knob head as a step in the right direction. When I read his excerpt and said it about myself, I felt somehow good. Like I wasn't hiding from reality anymore. Like I was done playing games with myself to convince myself that my looking at numbers was somehow out of my control or was just part of being a professional. Addicts often play feel-good games with themselves. Will seeing that help me control an addiction? I don't know. Time will tell.

Maybe my fall into metrification obsession is singular. In having spent time around academics, I suspect not. Us academics are good at seeing ourselves removed from the realities of the everyday. For example, from social media obsessions. We can bemoan how the need for likes, to justify opinions, on one's social media is leading to detrimental effects on knowledge exchange. At the same time, we can ignore isomorphic behaviors in our professional lives. If admitting it is step one, then maybe step two is collectively admitting it.

Can we start 'Metrification Obsessed Academics Anonymous'? The goal of the organization would be for all in the group to help each other from falling back into addictive patterns. I would benefit from being told "you're drifting back into knob head land" if, for example, my reviews of research papers started unfairly insisting that my work be cited (because that ups my metrics). Equally of value, perhaps more so, would be the academic equivalent of Al-Anon for friends and family of performance-metric obsessed academics.